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Sustainable energies – the beauty and the beast

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ABSTRACT

Energy consumption has been essential for Nations' development. Developing countries are highly populated and growing at a faster pace than already developed ones. Their willingness to reach a higher state of development is natural, which will inevitably mean the need for huge amounts of energy and resources. Moreover, they will generate huge amounts of gaseous and liquid effluents, and of wastes, triggering a need for much more efficient and cleaner technologies. Developed countries, however, face other problems, as they have established technologies, strategies and policies that are hard to change. Therefore, changing attitudes and strategic planning is vital to achieve a sustainable world. This change of attitudes is hard, and extremely dependent on the existence of a new kind of professionals who can, not only understand the diversity of problems and their implications, but also act as the link between the several *specialists* who can solve only particular problems. This calls for a multidisciplinary training at the higher education level, which has not been favoured. In this paper it will be discussed how to introduce in the engineering curricula the tools to educate such professionals, and how this strategy can be used to distinguish this

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new generation of technicians.

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INTRODUCTION

The energy-based development has driven Nations to an exponential growth in energy consumption. The fossil derived energy is becoming scarce to fulfil all the energy needs. Besides, the associated emissions and environmental impacts are driving scientists and decision makers towards both a new model of development based on renewable energy systems, as well as on more efficient energy systems. However, both have brought new challenges: a significant part of renewable energies is intrinsically unpredictable and presently only can be used in a low percentage, as the electric paradigm is based in control. New appliances are now not only more efficient but also nonlinear loads, because of the introduction of electronic controllers, which brought negative impact on the electric energy quality.

These evidences show that not everything that is renewable will be sustainable. *The Beauty* of being apparently more environmentally friend also causes problems that need solution. On the other hand, the non-renewable energies cannot be considered as *The Beast*, as their total elimination from the actual energy system cannot be achieved without a deep change of both human behaviour and of the energy system. The whole system has to be analysed in a life cycle thinking perspective, where non-renewable energy sources must be considered as one essential piece to supply the failures of the renewable sources, and all the appliances that are developed to reduce the energy consumption are submitted to deep analysis of their impacts.

To analyse such problems, two different approaches can be used, though, any of them is based on the existence of professionals who are multidisciplinary in nature. The first approach is to build teams that are led by senior experienced engineers (SEE), used to work in large teams of specialists; the second approach is to form teams that are led by junior multidisciplinary engineers (JME), used to analyse and discuss problems in multidisciplinary teams, including in their analysis not only the direct impacts but also the impacts that occur in different dimensions, and to anticipate potential problems. SEE have high associated costs and may have tendency to overestimate or underestimate potential problems. JME have lower associated costs and a natural willingness to let specialists present the advantages, whereas they can themselves anticipate the drawbacks.

Thus, multidisciplinary is now an advantage to solve problems such as the storage of surplus renewable energy produced for later use, or its immediate distribution to where it is needed by using smart grids, the mobility and transportation in modern mega cities, the integrated waste and effluents treatment with energy and/or biofuel production, or even the construction of Zero net Energy Buildings (ZEB), among others.

Therefore, this new model of development relies on a new class of environment and energy professionals, who are able to relate their particular expertise with all the other areas involved, and to understand the impacts of such systems. The time to explore

concepts and emerging technologies in a collaborative way has just started, bringing together engineers, researchers, decision makers and professionals from different areas. In fact, we can perceive that new and tighter targets towards sustainable development have been set by several countries, as from the Paris Agreement in December 2015. However, the path to reach them is a sensitive matter concerning to each country and no rules were set. Thus, more than ever, in this very moment it is critical to educate professionals who are able to plan truly sustainable systems.

We will discuss how to introduce in the engineering curricula the tools to educate such professionals, and how this strategy can be used to distinguish this new generation of technicians.

1 DEVELOPING AN ENGINEERING CURRICULUM

According to Feisel and Rosa [1] *“Engineering is a practicing profession, a profession devoted to harnessing and modifying the three fundamental resources that humankind has available for the creation of all technology: energy, materials, and information”*.

The Bologna Declaration on Higher Education (HE) [2] was the turning point when all the Portuguese HE Universities and Polytechnics had to change the model of their engineering curricula to a 3+2 years plan of studies. Up to then, different models co-existed, with 3+2 years in the Polytechnic and 5 years in the Universities. Nowadays, the 3 years graduation as a Bachelor in Engineering (*Licenciado em Engenharia*) allows one to develop a professional activity as an engineer with limited intervention, if the graduate comes from a Polytechnic. However, Universities that essentially have adopted and integrated model offering a 5 years course with an intermediate graduation as Bachelor in Sciences of Engineering (*Licenciado em Ciências de Engenharia*) in the 3rd year, do not recognize that these graduates have any engineering skills. The last 2 years are part of the graduation as MSc in Engineering, including a Master Thesis corresponding to at least 30 ECTS.

1.1 Graduation in Engineering

It has been a matter of discussion, if engineering curricula should start with a focused or with a comprehensive plan. The main advantage of the comprehensive plan, where students must contact with several matters, is that graduates learn, from a very early stage of their lives, how to interact and consider the different problems. However, they do not have enough time to deepen the knowledge, and therefore they may not really have the tools to understand the impacts of their decisions. This partially explains the relatively high rate of Dropouts in such courses.

On the other hand, the focused plan has the advantage of providing the students with enough tools to start a professional activity in a particular field of engineering, such as mechanical engineering, electrical engineering, civil engineering, geotechnical engineering, chemical engineering, etc. Being focused, students may not be aware of the need for interaction with other specialities, and therefore they may not develop the necessary skills for teamwork (not group work).

However, in our experience, we believe that younger students have generally much lower degree of autonomy and maturity that is needed for succeeding in graduation under the comprehensive plan.

1.2 Post-graduation: the MSc in Engineering

Depending on the HE system, the number of students who already are developing (or have developed) professional activity when they are studying in the MSc program can

be substantially different, whereas in the Polytechnic system this number can reach up to 90% [3], in the University system it is usually much below 25%.

This not only affects the *style of learning*, but also the motivation, the time available to attend classes and to study, and specially, the matters of interest. In fact, professionally active students often pose questions intrinsically linked with *problems* from real cases in their own jobs. This is not only important because the school acts as a trigger for the *solution* but also because the remaining students in class recognise the *global importance* of a given subject and increase their *trust* on the educator.

Additionally, having developed professional activity can be used as case study, or as a source of interaction between Academy and Industry, helping the creation of strong and long lasting ties between them.

The higher degree of maturity of the students in this 2nd cycle of studies allows one to address bigger challenges, as those that are derived from multidisciplinary problems. This is the reason why it should be preferred to organize the HE courses in engineering in such a way that the 1st cycle is focused in a particular field of engineering and the 2nd cycle can be more comprehensive.

2 EDUCATING ENGINEERS FOR SUSTAINABLE ENERGY SYSTEMS

Having decided that it is preferred to use the focused+generic plan in the 1st+2nd cycle, it was thus decided to plan a MSc in Sustainable Energies. This MSc program [4] receives graduates from any 1st cycle in Engineering, as well as graduates from other fields of sciences. However, the later may have to acquire skills in particular areas, such as Thermodynamics, Physics, etc.

2.1 Designing the course plan

The course plan was built upon multidepartmental teamwork. Representatives from all engineering departments at ISEP were involved in the design of this course, bringing their expertise in the particular scientific area of engineering as well as their knowledge on the scientific problems under study in the energy field. Already at this time, it was privileged the participation of those who were able (or who were willing to make an effort) to address and discuss multidisciplinary problems.

The result was a set of 8 mandatory plus a set of 5 out of 19 elective disciplines, each accounting for 6 ECTS, followed by a final Master Thesis (42 ECTS) [4].

2.2 Mandatory courses

The objectives of the mandatory courses is to provide all the students with the basic knowledge and skills in the energy sector, with a particular focus in the Environment and Natural Resources; Renewable Energy sources; Transfer Phenomena; Dynamic Control Systems; Management and Evaluation of Environmental Impacts; Energy Conversion Systems, and finally, Economical Analysis of Environment and Energy Projects. As the MSc receives students from different backgrounds, sometimes this means that the mandatory courses start with a kind of brief revision of basic concepts, and then they deepen the necessary disciplines.

2.3 Elective courses

These are the courses that allow each student to build his own professional profile, according to his preferences and style. Therefore, it is possible that a student chooses courses more oriented to higher energy efficiency, to sustainable buildings, to combustion systems, to biofuels production and characterization, to emissions treatment and minimization, air conditioning, distributed energy systems, energy

markets, or even entrepreneurship, among others. The electives are focused courses, usually appealing to previously acquired base knowledge.

3 DISCUSSION

It should be emphasized the high acceptance of this course and the enthusiasm of the students who attend it. Partly this is due to the fact that energy and sustainability are current and modern themes, for some, they are really a hot topic. However, students realize that there is still much to be developed in several areas of work and they genuinely intend to contribute with their attitude, efforts and skills.

In fact, it is motivating to develop solutions that contribute to a more sustainable world (The Beauty) but an intervention in an area has a chain effect in the system (The Beast), being only possible to solve the problems stepwisely.

When we take the example of public lighting using LED-based lamps, we know that the replacement of conventional lamps with LEDs resulted in a lower energy consumption. However, LED lamp power supply has a highly non-linear behaviour, causing harmonic distortion and greatly increasing electric power distribution losses [5]. Public lighting is an Electric Energy System area, whereas the lighting power supply belongs to the Electronics Engineering area. Furthermore, other problems arise from the extensive use of LED lamps, as is the case of the quality of light and the effects of single wavelength on human visual comfort (Electric Energy Systems), the problem of natural resources needed to supply the required amount of lamps (Mining, Geotechnical and Environmental Engineering), or last but not least important, the problem of the disposal and elimination of the spent LEDs when their end-of-life is reached (Environmental planning and management).

When we take such a kind of approach to the Electronical appliances, we notice that it is mandatory to apply a Life Cycle Analysis (LCA) methodology to the production of any new equipment in a large scale. The solution to this problem can only be designed through the collaborative work of professionals of all involved areas.

As referred in section 2 of this paper, the Master in Sustainable Energies was carefully designed in order to develop the technical and interpersonal skills, with a broad scope of disciplines taught by professors from six engineering departments of ISEP, who have succeeded in working together in the same collaborative path.

As an example of the success of this MSc, we can point out a geotechnical engineer who is working today with Bosch, a mechanical engineer who is working in a biofuels plant supplier or a civil engineer who is working in the wind energy sector, all of them as Master graduates.

4 CONCLUSION

The Master in Sustainable Energies has graduated professionals in the Energy sector with a focus in the engineering aspects, from 2011. The course has a comprehensive structure, and has received growing interest, not only at a National but also at an International level – Brazilian, Indian, Polish, German, Latvian, French, Spanish, Italian, Syrian, Nigerian, etc., students. Its graduates are all developing professional activity, regardless of their primary 1st cycle graduation program, in the energy sector.

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